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System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

In this work package CFD and experiments are used to determine whether flame-regulated flares can be used to lower hydrogen flaring emissions. Special focus is on the emissions of NO_x and unburnt hydrogen for regulated flares with different fuel flows, fuel hydrogen content and additional air in the burning mixture. For this a burner was converted to a flare. The experiments which were performed with this set-up are discussed in report D5E.1. The current report is focused on the CFD simulations performed with regards to this work.

In total 8 simulation cases are computed, which vary in fuel flow, hydrogen content of the fuel and additional air added to the burning mixture. These simulations use an unstructured mesh of the domain, which includes the burner geometry, a chimney and a portion of the surrounding air. RANS $k-\epsilon$ is used as a turbulence model, which inherently means that all simulations are steady. Consequently, the resulting flow fields are of averaged parameters. Furthermore, the simulations include full chemistry with 9 species and 22 reactions, radiation and turbulence-chemistry interaction.

The main conclusion of the simulations is that dilution of the flame leads to a reduction in both the amount of unburnt hydrogen escaping and production of NO_x. This dilution can be due to introducing additional air in the burning mixture or lowering the hydrogen content. Important to note here is that the dilution should not be done to such a degree that the a well-developed flame is not maintained anymore. Then the hydrogen largely just escapes. The fact that flame dilution is so effective in lowering emissions shows that flame-regulated flares are a viable strategy for reducing the environmental impact of hydrogen flaring.

Furthermore, the simulations show a strong correlation between temperatures and NO_x emissions, a phenomenon already well established. It shows that reducing the burning temperatures should be a priority when designing flares for hydrogen service.

Samenvatting

In dit werkpakket worden CFD en experimenten gebruikt om te bepalen of vlam-gereguleerde fakkels kunnen worden ingezet om waterstoffakkkel-emissies te verlagen. De focus ligt met name op de emissies van NO_x en onverbrande waterstof voor gereguleerde fakkels met verschillende brandstofdebieten, waterstofgehalten in de brandstof en extra lucht in het brandende mengsel. Hiervoor is een brander omgebouwd tot een fakkel. De experimenten die met deze opstelling zijn uitgevoerd, worden besproken in rapport D5E.1. Het huidige rapport richt zich op de CFD-simulaties die in het kader van dit werk zijn uitgevoerd.

In totaal zijn 8 simulatiecases gesimuleerd, die variëren in brandstofdebiet, waterstofgehalte van de brandstof en de hoeveelheid extra lucht die aan het brandende mengsel wordt toegevoegd. Deze simulaties maken gebruik van een unstructured mesh van het domein, dat de brander geometrie, een schoorsteen en een deel van de omgevingslucht omvat. Als turbulentie-model is RANS k- ϵ gebruikt, wat inherent betekent dat alle simulaties steady zijn. De resulterende stromingsvelden bestaan daardoor uit gemiddeldes van de relevante parameters. Daarnaast bevatten de simulaties volledige chemie met 9 componenten en 22 reacties, straling en interactie tussen turbulentie en chemie.

De belangrijkste conclusie uit de simulaties is dat verdunning van de vlam leidt tot een afname van zowel de hoeveelheid ontsnappende onverbrande waterstof als de productie van NO_x. Deze verdunning kan worden bereikt door extra lucht aan het brandende mengsel toe te voegen of door het waterstofgehalte te verlagen. Het is hierbij belangrijk op te merken dat de verdunning niet zo ver mag gaan dat er geen goed ontwikkelde vlam meer in stand blijft. In dat geval ontsnapt de waterstof grotendeels onverbrand. Het feit dat vlamverdunning zo effectief is in het verlagen van emissies laat zien dat vlam-gereguleerde fakkels een goede strategie zijn om de milieubelasting van waterstoffakkelen te verminderen.

Verder laten de simulaties een sterke correlatie zien tussen temperatuur en NO_x-emissies, een verschijnsel dat al goed bekend is. Dit onderstreept dat het verlagen van de verbrandingstemperatuur een belangrijk aandachtspunt moet zijn bij het ontwerpen van fakkels voor waterstoftoepassingen.

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1. Introduction

During operation of hydrogen gas networks, pipes will need to be emptied of their gas. This can be for maintenance purposes, or in the process of transitioning from natural gas to hydrogen. This emptying of the pipes happens as much as possible with methods like recompression where the gas can be re-used. However, there are circumstances where that is not possible and the gas is disposed of using mobile flares.

At this point it is unclear how well the flares can handle varying composition of the fuel. It is foreseen that they should be able to deal with varying mixtures of hydrogen/nitrogen and of hydrogen/natural gas. Therefore, this work package is aimed to investigate if flame-regulated flares can be used to limit emissions of hydrogen flaring under different conditions.

The focus of the research is mobile flares for incidental use, with a special focus on *regulated flares* which can regulate the amount of air in the burning mixture. The main goal of the flaring is to have as little unburnt fuel as possible emitted to the atmosphere. Secondary goal is to limit the NO_x emissions as much as possible. This is especially relevant for hydrogen flares as the higher burning temperatures increase the production of NO_x when compared to natural gas.

This work package consists of two parts: an experimental part and a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modelling part. The results of the physical experiments are described in report D5E.1, while this report describes the results of the fluid dynamics modelling. Even though the results are reported in two separate deliverables, the work has been done in tight cooperation and a lot of interaction. The simulations have been performed in parallel with the experimental testing.

This report will start by detailing the methodology of the CFD simulations in Chapter 2. The results of the different simulation cases are discussed in Chapter 3. Finally, the results are used to draw conclusions in Chapter 4.

2. Methodology

All simulations are performed using ANSYS Fluent 23.1 [1].

2.1 Simulation domain

The simulation domain is defined around the burner geometry as received from the burner manufacturer. First, it is described how this geometry is incorporated in the simulation, after which the focus is on the chimney and the rest of the domain.

2.1.1 Burner geometry

The selected burner for the experiments and CFD simulations is Dunphy TG04.65 hydrogen burner and the geometry included in the simulations is based on the geometry received from the manufacturer and displayed in Figure 2.1. The hydrogen enters the burner and is brought to the top of the burner through six tubes. The air flow to the top is controlled by a fan.

Figure 2.1 Cross-section of the burner geometry as received from the manufacturer. The hydrogen flow is indicated in orange and the air path is indicated in blue.

A close up of the burner tip geometry is included in Figure 2.2 which shows the six nozzles through which the hydrogen is transported, after which the hydrogen is introduced into the burning mixture in a tangential fashion. Also visible is a notched plate which steers the air in the opposite direction as the hydrogen in order to enhance the mixing. Air also flows through the opening outside the plate.

Figure 2.2 Close up of the burner tip showing the six nozzles through which the hydrogen is transported and a notched plate through and around which the air is supplied.

It should be noted that the geometry as received from the manufacturer and included in the simulations deviates from the as-built physical experimental set-up as shown in Figure 2.3. Specifically, the configuration of the hydrogen nozzles is different than expected. The nozzles in the physical set-up are not uniform in height, hole size or direction of the hole.

Figure 2.3 Close up of the as-built burner tip as included in the physical experimental set-up.

2.1.2 Chimney geometry

Included in the simulation set-up is also a chimney around the burner. This chimney has a diameter of 350 mm and is 750 mm in length. The distance from the bottom of the chimney to the burner tip is approximately 300 mm.

Figure 2.4 Simulation geometry including the burner and chimney.

The measurements of the chimney included in the simulations deviate from the chimney geometry as included in the physical experimental set-up. There a chimney of 1200 mm length is used where the bottom is located approximately 250 mm below the burner tip.

2.1.3 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions used to model the burner tip are shown in Figure 2.5. The air through the notched plate is modelled by a velocity boundary condition. The velocity is specified in the counter-tangential direction in order to approximate the effect of the plate notches. The flow around the plate is modelled through a mass-flow boundary condition. The fraction of air flowing through the plate and around the plate is based on the flow area in the CAD model received from the manufacturer. This means that 80.3% of the air flows around the plate, straight upwards. The remaining 19.7% of the air is introduced in the simulation by the swirling velocity boundary condition.

Figure 2.5 Boundary conditions used to model the burner tip. Gray indicates a wall, the air plate is indicated in purple and the air inlet around the plate is indicated in pink.

The rest of the simulation domain is shown in Figure 2.6. The hydrogen inlet nozzles are simulated for 120 mm, which corresponds to around 10 diameters. The hydrogen is introduced using a mass-flow boundary condition. The farfield is a cylinder of 700 mm diameter and 850 mm length, positioned 100 mm below the tip of the chimney. It is modelled as a pressure-outlet. It should be noted that a 0.1 m/s of air velocity boundary condition is imposed at the bottom of the chimney to prevent unphysical, numerical build up of hydrogen near the bottom of the chimney. This approximates the suction of additional air through gaps at the bottom of the chimney.

Figure 2.6 Simulation domain for the CFD simulations, showing the different boundary conditions.

2.1.4 Simulation mesh

The simulation mesh used in the simulation is shown in Figure 2.7. First, an unstructured tetrahedral mesh was created. This was converted to a polyhedral mesh using Fluent in order to reduce the number of cells and to improve convergence. The mesh contains 1.5 million polyhedral cells and includes an area of refinement near the tip of the burner where most of the chemistry is expected to take place. As we are not interested in the area close to the wall no additional refinement was placed there. The minimum orthogonal quality of the mesh is 0.10 and the maximum aspect ratio is 17.3.

Figure 2.7 Simulation mesh as used in the simulations. The full mesh is shown on the left, while the refinement near the burner tip is displayed on the right.

2.2 Simulation Cases

A description of the different simulation cases is included in Table 2.1. The nominal case burns 10 kg/h of 100% hydrogen and injects an air flow which would constitute 3% excess oxygen if all the hydrogen would be burned. The air in the simulation consists of 21 mol-% oxygen and 79 mol-% nitrogen.

Aside from the nominal case, the influence of carrying three parameters on the flare behaviour will be researched: 1) the influence of the mass flows, 2) the influence of the fuel hydrogen content and 3) the influence of the air content of the burning mixture. When the fuel hydrogen content is varied, the rest of the fuel consists of nitrogen.

Table 2.1 Description of the simulation cases included in the analysis.

No	Name	Fuel [kg/h]	Air [kg/h]	Fuel H ₂ content	Excess O ₂
1	Nominal case	10	351.3	100%	3%
2	Maximum flow	20	702.5	100%	3%
3	Minimum flow	3	105.3	100%	3%
4	80 mol-% H ₂	10	351.3	80 mol-%	
5	80 mass-% H ₂	10	351.3	80 mass-%	
6	10% excess O ₂	10	378.6	100%	10%
7	20% excess O ₂	10	425.9	100%	20%
8	40% excess O ₂	10	567.9	100%	40%

2.3 Simulation settings

As stated previously, the simulations are performed using ANSYS Fluent 23.1 [1]. The simulations are all steady state RANS simulations, which means that it solves for the time averaged velocity and other fields. The pressure-based solver is used in conjunction with the absolute velocity formulation and the influence of gravity is included. Density is computed according to incompressible ideal gas.

Simulations are performed for a pressure of 1 bar, an outside temperature of 10 °C and a corresponding air density of 1.242 kg/m³.

The CFD methodology used solves the following equations:

- Continuity, momentum (in 3 directions), energy
- Turbulence (Realizable k-ε [2])
- 9 species (Z22 Zettervall mechanism [3])
- Radiation (Discrete Ordinates Model [4])
- Pollutant NO_x (thermal NO_x: extended Zeldovich [5])

More detailed information about the models used, the discretization method and boundary condition implementation is given below.

2.3.1 Models

In order to model the influence of the turbulence on the flow field, the realizable k-ε turbulence model [2] is used in conjunction with enhanced wall treatment and full buoyancy effects.

The species transport is modelled using the Z22 Zettervall kinetic mechanism [3]. This kinetic mechanism for hydrogen combustion includes 9 species and 22 reactions, the reactions and specific reaction rate constants are included in Appendix A which include the species H₂, O₂, H₂O, N₂, H, O, OH, HO₂ and H₂O₂. Furthermore, the thermodynamic and transport databases from San Diego are used [6]. In order to model the interaction between chemistry and turbulence, the Eddy Dissipation Concept (EDC) model is used which assumes all reactions occur in smaller scales, as a constant pressure reactor with initial conditions taken as the current species and temperatures [7]. For the species transport, the *diffusion energy source* and *full multicomponent diffusion* options of Fluent are applied.

The radiation is modelled through the discrete ordinated model of Fluent [4]. For this simulation 6 theta divisions of 1 pixel and 6 phi divisions of 1 pixel are used.

Lastly, the NO_x formation is modelled in the simulation through a separate pollutant NO_x model as the NO_x formation chemistry is not included in the kinetic mechanism to keep the computational

effort manageable. Only the thermal NO_x model is used which applies the extended Zeldovich mechanism [5]. This mechanism uses the reversible reactions specified below and assumes equilibrium values of temperature, O₂, N₂, O and OH concentrations.

Thermal formation of NO_x is the dominant source for hydrogen flames, however other mechanisms also play a role. To model this the NO_x needs to be included in the kinetic mechanism, making the simulations much more computationally expensive. Therefore, it is chosen to only include the thermal formation of NO_x. This means that the NO_x formation is slightly underpredicted, as long as the temperature field is properly simulated.

2.3.2 Solution Discretization Methods

An overview of the different discretization methods applied in the simulations is given in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Overview of discretization methods applied in the simulations.

Parameter	Scheme
Pressure-velocity coupling	SIMPLE
Flux-type	Rie-Chow: Distance based
Gradient	Least-squared distance based
Pressure	PRESTO!
Momentum	2 nd order upwind
TKE	2 nd order upwind
TKE dissipation	2 nd order upwind
Species	2 nd order upwind
Energy	2 nd order upwind
Discrete Ordinates	1 st order upwind
Pollutant NO	2 nd order upwind
Pseudo-time method	Local time step (Courant no: 5)
Warped-face gradient correction	On
High order term relaxation	0.25 (all variables)

2.3.3 Boundary Conditions

The fuel inlet and air inlet around the plate are modelled as mass flow inlets, while the air inlet plate and chimney bottom are modelled as velocity inlets, as described before. All inlets use the default 5% turbulence intensity, and turbulent viscosity ratio of 10. The inflow temperature is 10 °C and for radiation purposes the inlets are modelled as opaque, with an internal emissivity of 1.

The outflow is modelled as a pressure outlet without backflow prevention and a temperature of 10 °C. The farfield is transparent to radiation in the simulations.

Lastly, all walls are modelled as stationary non-slip walls. Only the chimney is modelled as a mixed thermal boundary condition. This means that both the convective cooling and the cooling due to external radiation emission are included. For these calculations a heat transfer coefficient of 10 W/(m² K), a 10 °C free stream temperature, 0.9 external emissivity and 1 cm wall thickness are used. For the internal radiation the internal emissivity and diffuse fraction are set to 0.9.

3. Results

In order to gain a better understanding of the burner flame behaviour according to the simulations, first the results for the nominal case (10 kg/h H₂, 3% excess O₂) will be discussed in detail. Then, the effect of adjusting different parameters on the flame behaviour will be investigated. Detailed figures for all simulation cases are included in Appendix B.

3.1 Nominal case results

The nominal case included a fuel flow of 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess air flow. Figure 3.1 shows the velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in the simulation domain. These figures show that the velocity is highest near the hydrogen nozzles and around the plate. Furthermore, they show a core of swirling flow of air in one direction, due to the notched plate. Around this core is a swirl of counter-rotating flow of hydrogen due to the orientation of the nozzle holes. These swirls are contained by the air flowing around the plate.

Figure 3.1 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the nominal case with 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

The simulated temperature in the domain is shown in Figure 3.2, as is the simulated mass fraction of NO_x throughout the domain. Figure 3.2 shows that for the nominal simulation case, the temperatures in the simulation are high, locally approaching the adiabatic flame temperature of hydrogen (2527 K). Also, Figure 3.2 shows that concentrations of NO_x are highest at the top of the domain where temperatures are also highest. This can be explained by the fact that the simulation only includes the thermal NO_x model, which directly links the NO_x production to the temperature.

Figure 3.2 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

The species of the main reagents of the flame chemistry, hydrogen and oxygen, are shown in Figure 3.3. It can be seen that the hydrogen is mainly present in a cone with oxygen present on the outside and bottom of the cone. The oxygen and hydrogen concentrations drop higher up in the domain due to them being used up in the burning of the flame.

Figure 3.3 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

Lastly, the main end product of the burning process, water vapor is shown in Figure 3.4. This figure also shows the OH concentration. This is the main radical of the hydrogen burning process and is a good indicator of where the burning reactions are taking place. Therefore, it shows the location of the flame front.

Figure 3.4 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

3.2 Effects of changing the fuel flow

The temperature profiles at the top of the domain are compared for different hydrogen fuel flows in Figure 3.5. It can be concluded that the temperatures for the minimum fuel flow case are much lower than for higher flows. Lower fuel flow means that less heat is generated, which explains the lower temperatures.

The temperature profiles do not differ a lot for the higher fuel flows. This can be explained by the fact that for these fuel flows the temperatures reached are already high, approaching the adiabatic flame temperature. Therefore, they cannot increase even further.

Figure 3.5 Horizontal temperature profiles at the top of the domain for varying burner hydrogen fuel flows.

Looking at the NO_x concentration profiles at the top of the domain in Figure 3.6, it can be concluded that the concentrations are clearly highest for the nominal fuel flow of 10 kg/h. This might be a bit surprising as one would maybe expect NO_x production to be highest for the largest fuel flows. However, NO_x production is strongly linked to high temperatures. In Figure 3.5 it was shown that the temperatures do not differ a lot between the simulation cases with 10 kg/h and 20 kg/h. The fact that the 10 kg/h case has significantly higher NO_x concentrations could indicate that this case has a larger volume where hydrogen/air ratios are closer to optimal and burn temperatures are higher.

Figure 3.6 Horizontal profiles of NO_x mass fraction at the top of the domain for varying burner hydrogen fuel flows.

The hydrogen concentration profiles at the top of the domain are shown in Figure 3.7. This shows that approximately all the hydrogen is burnt for the minimum flow case. However, for higher fuel flows some hydrogen escapes the flame.

Figure 3.7 Horizontal profiles of hydrogen mol fraction at the top of the domain for varying burner hydrogen fuel flows.

Lastly, an overview of the NO_x emissions per kg hydrogen burnt and amount of hydrogen escaping the burner flame is shown in Figure 3.8. A strong dependency between the fraction of hydrogen escaping the burner flame and the hydrogen fuel flow is visible. Higher fuel flows mean higher flow velocities, which could mean that the burning chemistry is not fast enough to burn all fuel.

The highest NO_x emissions are seen for the nominal fuel flow. As previously explained this strongly correlates to the temperatures in the domain. It could be speculated that the burner was designed to have a large area with uniform high temperatures. The minimum and maximum fuel cases are at the edges of the operating range the burner was designed for. This could mean that the temperature field is less uniform and lower in magnitude, leading to less NO_x production.

Figure 3.8 Overview of NO_x emissions and unburnt hydrogen for different burner hydrogen fuel flows.

3.3 Effects of changing the hydrogen content in the fuel

The temperature profiles at the top of the domain for varying fuel hydrogen content, included in Figure 3.9, show more variation than for the varying fuel flow.

The most striking deviation is the low temperatures for the simulation case with 80 mol-% hydrogen and 20 mol-% nitrogen. This can be explained by the fact that these mol percentages are the equivalent to a mixture with approximately 22.5 mass-% hydrogen. A fuel flow of 10 kg/h with this fuel leads to an actual hydrogen flow lower than the lower limit of the burner. Therefore, the flame is not well developed. The fact that the temperatures are higher than the ambient, do show that some ignition is present. However, it is far from the well-developed flames of the other two simulations.

The temperatures at the top of the domain are lower for the fuel with 80 mass-% hydrogen than for the pure hydrogen fuel. This is explained by less hydrogen and more nitrogen being present. This means that less energy is generated by the burning process, and this energy needs to heat up more gas.

Figure 3.9 Horizontal temperature profiles at the top of the domain for varying burner hydrogen fuel flows.

Considering the nitrogen concentrations at the top of the domain, shown in Figure 3.10, it can be concluded that the non-developed flame for the fuel with 80 mol-% produces approximately no NO_x. Furthermore, the lower temperatures for the 80 mass-% hydrogen fuel mixture lead to significantly less NO_x production for this flame than for the pure hydrogen flame.

Figure 3.10 Horizontal profiles of NO_x mass fraction at the top of the domain for varying burner fuel hydrogen content.

The hydrogen concentrations at the top of the domain are shown in Figure 3.11 show that a lot of hydrogen escapes the burning process for the flame with 80 mol-% fuel. Furthermore, it is shown that the fuel containing an 80/20 mass-% mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen burns the hydrogen better than the pure hydrogen flame.

Figure 3.11 Horizontal profiles of hydrogen mol fraction at the top of the domain for varying burner fuel hydrogen content.

Lastly, an overview of the NO_x emissions and unburnt hydrogen escaping the burning process is shown in Figure 3.12 for the varying fuel hydrogen contents. This shows that lowering the hydrogen content in the fuel lowers the amount of NO_x generated and hydrogen escaping the burning process for this burner set-up. However, this only works as long as enough hydrogen is in the fuel for a well developed flame, otherwise almost all hydrogen just escapes in stead of burning.

Figure 3.12 Overview of NO_x emissions and unburnt hydrogen for different burner fuel hydrogen content.

3.4 Effects of air-content in the burning mixture

The last variation investigated is the effect of introducing additional air in the burning mixture. This would be the main functionality which comes with using a regulated flare in stead of a standard non-regulated one.

The temperature profiles in Figure 3.13 show a clear trend of reducing temperature with increasing additional air. This is due to approximately the same amount of heat being produced, but being distributed over more gas, leading to lower temperatures. At 40% O₂ excess the temperature stays below 1800K which is the threshold for thermal NO_x.

Figure 3.13 Horizontal temperature profiles at the top of the domain for varying amounts of excess air in the burning mixture.

As seen in previously discussed results, there is a strong correlation between temperature and the production of NO_x. This is further confirmed by the NO_x concentration profiles shown in Figure 3.14. Furthermore, as could be expected from the temperature plot, no NO_x is formed for the simulation with the highest amount of excess oxygen.

Figure 3.14 Horizontal profiles of NO_x mass fraction at the top of the domain for varying amounts of excess air in the burning mixture.

Next, Figure 3.15 shows the hydrogen concentrations at the top of the domain. Interestingly, there seems to be a strong negative correlation between the amount of hydrogen escaping the burner flame and the amount of excess air in the burning mixture. This indicates that by adding more air to there are less regions in the burner flow field where the hydrogen/air ratios are outside the burning limits.

Figure 3.15 Horizontal profiles of hydrogen mol fraction at the top of the domain for varying amounts of excess air in the burning mixture.

The results of the previously discussed profiles are summarized in the plot included in Figure 3.16. This plot shows the development of the fraction of hydrogen escaping the burner flame and NO_x emissions for the different simulation cases. It is clear that, for this burner set-up, adding more air to the burning mixture leads to reduced NO_x emissions and more of the hydrogen fuel being burnt.

Figure 3.16 Overview of NO_x emissions and unburnt hydrogen for different amounts of excess air in the burning mixture.

4. Conclusions

This study used CFD simulation to evaluate the flow and burning behaviour in a regulated flare set-up for different fuel flows, fuel compositions and gas mixtures. The simulations provide detailed insight into velocity fields, pressure distributions, and turbulence structures inside the flare system. Overall, the results show that the main flow features are strongly influenced by the geometry of the flare and the distribution of the incoming gas streams.

A strong influence is seen of the fuel flow on the amount of unburnt hydrogen escaping and NO_x generated. For the fraction of hydrogen escaping it is clear that higher flows lead to higher velocities and a larger portion of the fuel remaining unburnt. The relation between the amount of NO_x generated and the fuel flow is not so straightforward. This is due to the fact that there is a strong correlation between the generation of NO_x and the burning temperature. It is speculated that the temperature in the domain are generally highest for the nominal fuel flow case as that is in the middle of the designed operation range of the burner used as a flare in this set-up. This could indicate that NO_x emissions of flares can be limited if they were to be designed for minimum burning temperature.

Reducing the fuel hydrogen content in the simulations lead to lower NO_x emissions and less hydrogen remaining unburnt. Again, the lower NO_x emissions can be attributed to a lower burning temperature. An important note for this is that the fuel hydrogen content remains high enough to maintain a well-developed flame.

Lastly, the simulations showed that adding additional air to the burning mixture reduces both the NO_x emissions and efficiency of the hydrogen combustion.

In general, it can be concluded that diluting the hydrogen flame, either by lowering the fuel hydrogen content or introducing additional air in the burning mixture, has a favourable effect on the amount of NO_x being generated and amount of hydrogen remaining unburnt. Therefore, using regulated flares has strong advantages to be used for hydrogen flaring as they have the capability to do just that.

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A. Z22 Zettervall combustion mechanism

Table A.1 Z22 Zettervall combustion reaction mechanism and specific reaction rate constants. E_a is the activation energy in [cal/mol], α is the pre-exponential exponent and A is the pre-exponential coefficient in [$\text{cm}^3/(\text{mol s K}^{\alpha})$] and [$\text{cm}^6/(\text{mol}^2 \text{s K}^{\alpha})$] for vi-molecular and tri-molecular reactions respectively [3]

No.	Reactions	A	α	E_a	Third-body chaperon efficiencies
1	$\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{HO}_2$	7.40E05	2.43	53500	
2	$\text{H}_2 + \text{M} \rightarrow 2 \text{H} + \text{M}$	4.57E19	-1.40	841.3	H/1.0/ H ₂ /2.5/ H ₂ O/12.0/ H ₂ O ₂ /1.0/ HO ₂ /1.0/ N ₂ /1.0/ O/1.0/ O ₂ /1.0/ OH/1.0/
3	$\text{H}_2 + \text{HO}_2 \rightarrow \text{H} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$	3.00E06	2.0	2100	
4	$\text{H} + \text{O}_2 \Rightarrow \text{O} + \text{OH}$	2.45E14	0.0	16800	
5	$\text{O} + \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H} + \text{O}_2$	1.20E13	0.0	690	
6	$\text{H}_2 + \text{O} \Rightarrow \text{H} + \text{OH}$	1.80E10	1.0	8826	
7	$\text{H} + \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{O}$	8.00E9	1.0	6760	
8	$\text{H}_2 + \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.17E9	1.3	3626	
9	$\text{H} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{OH}$	5.09E9	1.3	18588	
10	$2 \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}$	6.00E8	1.3	0.0	
11	$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O} \Rightarrow 2 \text{OH}$	5.90E9	1.3	17029	
12	$\text{H} + \text{O}_2 + \text{M} \Rightarrow \text{HO}_2 + \text{M}$	1.80E18	-0.8	0.0	H ₂ /1.0/ H ₂ O/6.5/ N ₂ /0.4/ O ₂ /0.4/
13	$\text{H} + \text{HO}_2 \Rightarrow 2 \text{OH}$	1.50E14	0.0	1004	
14	$\text{H} + \text{HO}_2 \Rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	2.50E13	0.0	700	
15	$\text{HO}_2 + \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$	2.00E13	0.0	1000	
16	$2 \text{HO}_2 \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{O}_2$	8.00E13	0.0	0.0	
17	$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{M} \Rightarrow 2 \text{OH} + \text{M}$	1.30E17	0.0	34500	
18	$2 \text{OH} + \text{M} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{M}$	9.86E14	0.0	-5070	
19	$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{OH} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HO}_2$	1.00E13	0.0	1800	
20	$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{HO}_2 \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{OH}$	2.86E13	0.0	32790	
21	$\text{H} + \text{OH} + \text{M} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{M}$	2.20E22	-2.0	0.0	
22	$2 \text{H} + \text{M} \Rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \text{M}$	1.80E18	-1.0	0.0	

B. Detailed simulation results

B.1 Case 1 (nominal): 10 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 3% excess air

Figure B.1 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the nominal case with 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.2 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.3 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.4 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the nominal simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

B.2 Case 2: 20 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 3% excess air

Figure B.5 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 20 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.6 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 20 kg/h of pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.7 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 20 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.8 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 20 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

B.3 Case 3: 3 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 3% excess air

Figure B.9 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 3 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.10 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 3 kg/h of pure hydrogen fuel flow and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.11 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 3 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

Figure B.12 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 3 kg/h of pure hydrogen and 3% excess oxygen.

B.4 Case 4: 10 kg/h, 80 mol-% hydrogen

Figure B.13 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 10 kg/h of 80 mol-% hydrogen fuel flow.

Figure B.14 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h of 80 mol-% hydrogen fuel flow.

Figure B.15 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h of 80 mol-% hydrogen.

Figure B.16 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h of 80 mol-% hydrogen.

B.5 Case 5: 10 kg/h, 80 mass-% hydrogen

Figure B.17 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 10 kg/h 80 mass-% hydrogen fuel flow.

Figure B.18 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h 80 mass-% hydrogen fuel flow.

Figure B.19 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h 80 mass-% hydrogen fuel flow.

Figure B.20 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h 80 mass-% hydrogen.

B.6 Case 6: 10 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 10% excess air

Figure B.21 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 10% excess oxygen.

Figure B.22 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 10% excess oxygen.

Figure B.23 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 10% excess oxygen.

Figure B.24 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h pure hydrogen and 10% excess oxygen.

B.7 Case 7: 10 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 20% excess air

Figure B.25 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 20% excess oxygen.

Figure B.26 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 20% excess oxygen.

Figure B.27 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 20% excess oxygen.

Figure B.28 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h pure hydrogen and 20% excess oxygen.

B.8 Case 8: 10 kg/h, 100% hydrogen, 40% excess air

Figure B.29 Velocity magnitude and tangential velocity in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case with 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 40% excess oxygen.

Figure B.30 Simulated temperature and NOx mass fraction in a cross-section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 40% excess oxygen.

Figure B.31 Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including 10 kg/h pure hydrogen fuel flow and 40% excess oxygen.

Figure B.32 Water vapor and OH concentrations, in mol fraction, in a cross section of the simulation domain for the simulation case including a fuel flow of 10 kg/h pure hydrogen and 40% excess oxygen.

C. Comparing flaring experiments and CFD results

Introduction

In WP5e of the HyDelta 4 project, two activities were carried out on the flaring of H₂ gas mixtures. The objective of this work package is to investigate whether flame-regulated flares can be used to reduce emissions during hydrogen flaring. The focus is on reducing emissions of NO_x and unburnt hydrogen using a regulated flare operating at different fuel flow rates, fuel hydrogen contents, and levels of additional air in the combustion mixture.

The experiments were carried out by KIWA and are described in report D5E.1, while the CFD simulations were performed by TNO and are detailed in Report D5E.2.

In both tasks, the ratios and amounts of H₂, air, and N₂ were varied. Although similar cases were tested and simulated, a one-to-one comparison was unfortunately not possible. In addition, the experiments were performed outdoors under varying weather conditions, which could not be included in the CFD simulations. Therefore, only overall trends can be compared.

In this document, the results of the two tasks are compared and analyzed, with particular emphasis on trends in H₂ and NO_x emissions and temperatures.

Decreasing NO_x with increasing air (O₂) excess

The first trend visible in both approaches is that, as the mixture becomes leaner (i.e., with excess oxygen), NO_x emissions decrease. This can be explained by the lower flame temperature, caused by a lower amount of H₂ relative to the total flow rate. Most of the NO_x generated is so-called thermal NO_x, which forms when the (local) temperature exceeds approximately 1750 K. Figure A1 shows this trend for the CFD results (left) and the experiments (right).

Figure A1: Trends in NO_x emissions as a function of λ / excess O₂. Left: CFD (blue line). Right: experiments at different loads.

Increasing H₂ emissions at high λ

The next trend is that, as the mixture becomes very lean, H₂ emissions increase. This can be attributed to combustion becoming unstable when little fuel is present. Due to turbulence, parts of the mixture can fall below the flammability limit and therefore not combust. This effect is more evident in the experiments than in the CFD simulations because the simulations assume an idealized environment and do not include changing outdoor weather conditions.

This is illustrated in Figure A2, where an increase in H₂ is observed at high λ or at low fuel H₂ content.

Figure A2 H₂ emissions as a function of λ / fuel composition. Left: CFD results.

Temperature

When comparing the measured and computed chimney wall temperatures, the measured temperatures are higher than those computed. At higher load, the experimental temperatures remain approximately the same as for the 330 kW load (Table A1), whereas the CFD results show an increase in temperature (Figure A3). A difference that was found between the simulations and the experiments is the direction of the flame jets. In the experiments the flames are directed outward to the chimney wall, whereas in the simulation the flames are directed upwards to the exit/top of the chimney. Furthermore, for hydrogen flames there is a difference in the radiative heat transfer coefficient (the main source of heat towards the chimney in the simulation) which is considerably lower than the convective heat transfer coefficient (the main source of heat towards the chimney in the experiments). Both these effects might explain the higher experimental temperatures, as well as the relative low temperature increase due to higher loads.

Table A2 Measured temperatures on outside of the chimney at different loads

Avg Heat input [kW]	T_1 [°C]	T_2 [°C]	T_3 [°C]	T_4 [°C]
120	648	644	628	610
331	760	755	725	723
490	761	772	710	745

Figure A3 Contour plots of outside wall temperature for (left) 10 kg/h (330 kW) and (right) 20 kg/h (660 kW) loads.

Discussion

Overall, the results show that increasing λ (i.e., operating leaner) reduces NO_x emissions, which is desirable. However, if the mixture becomes too lean (high λ), not all hydrogen combusts, which is undesirable. Therefore, the use of a controlled (flame-regulated) flare is recommended, for which an optimum operating point can be identified that minimizes both NO_x and unburnt H_2 emissions. The optimum setting will depend on the specific burner/flare design and its operating conditions.